

Millennials and the use of social networking sites as a job searching tool

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ABSTRACT

This research is conducted to examine the factors that influence the behavioural intention of millennials in using SNS when seeking for a job. The data was collected from respondents who are from the generation Y demographic and actively looking for jobs. The respondents must possess some experience in using SNS when job hunting. The data was then gathered and analyzed using partial least square (PLS) which encompasses the measurement and structural models of the study. The findings revealed that three of the constructs as applied in TAM are statistically significant to behavioural intention. The three factors that influenced the job seekers' intention to use SNSs as a job search tool are; perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and privacy concerns. All these factors are elements which contribute to and have a significant relationship with job seekers' intention to use SNSs, as verified using PLS data analysis. The recruiters or employers who intend to adopt SNSs in the recruitment process are advised to design the recruitment plan regarding the utilization of SNSs to be more convenient and user-friendly. This study provides insight and knowledge regarding the impact of technology in online job application and hiring processes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recruitment is a crucial component of the human resource management (HRM) department in any organization. Recruitment involves seeking out, engaging and assessing potential employees suited to various roles within the organization. It is tremendously difficult to discover and obtain such candidates, and this requires human resource (HR) managers to apply different tactics in the efforts to recruit workers. These days, recruitment processes can be conducted conventionally or through e-recruitment systems, which function through information technology tools. Conventional recruitment approaches include putting advertisements in newspapers regarding vacant positions, utilizing executive search firms, and engaging recruitment agencies which refer relevant employees to the organization [1-5]. The development of technology has enabled all these methods to be carried out via e-recruitment or other Internet-based job application services.

The age of e-recruitment has significantly changed the recruitment process as a whole. However, older recruitment approaches should not be discarded entirely, but used in ways that complement electronic-based methods. According to Kaur new technology must not fully replace traditional processes, which can function to compensate for the flaws of electronic systems and foster a quick and effective recruitment process [6].

Social networking sites (SNSs) are among the most popular online platforms in current times. It is extensively utilized by HR managers and job seekers due to its convenience and efficiency. One can use SNSs in order to seek out available vacancies in organizations, particularly through career-centric sites like LinkedIn [7]. The organization can also reach a wide range of potential employees with various qualifications and competencies [8]. Additionally, with well-structured and organized processes, SNSs can aid a firm in saving expenses and ensuring that the recruitment approach is less time-consuming, by cutting down on the period needed for processing information [9]. In order to enhance the quality of the job applications, it is presumed that someone who utilizes e-recruitment options is already computer literate and capable of working with new technology.

The yearly worldwide survey, the Kelly Global Workforce Index (KGWI), is conducted by the renowned recruitment firm, Kelly Services, and referred to in a report in the Malay Mail. This survey discovered that Malaysians rank far above the regional average rate in terms of individuals using SNSs as a platform for job seeking, as opposed to traditional methods. This encompasses 67 per cent of the total number of 5,147 respondents. Additionally, 62 per cent of respondents also described being approached with offers for vacant positions on social networking sites, and another 28 per cent also claim that the job offers eventually led to successful employment.

Despite this, in [10] asserts that SNSs cannot be an effective method for recruitment processes because it does nothing to enhance the recruiter's powers of judgement and discernment. Kilpatrick also argues that SNSs as a platform is not capable of facilitating the huge number of relationships between potential employees and employers. Reiners proposes that the success of SNSs in the recruitment process can be achieved by ensuring that everyone involved is aware of the social dynamics in creating and engaging with social media profiles. As such, the concept of the technology acceptance model (TAM) is adopted as the foundation used in order to better comprehend the function of social networking sites as recruitment aids. The researcher explores elements including ease of use, perceived usefulness, and issues regarding privacy. Thus, the objective of the current study is to examine the intentions of generation Y to utilize SNSs as a job seeking tool.

2. METHODOLOGY

Data was gathered from 188 respondents who are part of generation Y and are in the process of looking for work. The respondents must have a degree of experience in utilizing SNS within their job search efforts. The instrument for perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness were derived from [11-15]. Other items such as privacy concerns were derived while behavioural intention was derived from [16]. The items were tested through a five point Likert scale where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree. The data was gathered and analyzed through partial least square (PLS) which examines the structural model and measurement model of the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Measurement model

Convergent validity describes the extent to which multiple items are capable of measuring the same concept. In [17] states that the evaluation of a measurement model involves composite reliability (CR), factor loadings, and average variance extracted (AVE). This is shown in Table 1. The acceptable value for loadings must exceed 0.5 while the CR must be over 0.7. Based on the results, the eight items of behavioral intention (CR=0.891, AVE=0.541), four items of perceived ease of use (CR=0.808, AVE=0.517), four items of privacy concerns (CR=0.801, AVE=0.503), and four items of perceived usefulness (CR=0.891, AVE=0.541) all exhibit that the values of factor loading, composite reliability and AVE exceeded the acceptable values. Some items were removed as a result of low factor loading. These are the items EOU2, EOU3, EOU6 and EOU7, four items of privacy1, privacy2, privacy 4, privacy5, and one item of BI1.

After verifying the convergent validity, the process to evaluate the discriminant validity using the [18] approach was carried out. Amin, Thurasamy, Aldakhil and Kaswuri explain discriminant validity as the item which differentiates between constructs, and is applied to testing items through the process of comparing the AVE with squared correlations values, or comparing the square root of the AVE with correlations values. The correlation values in the diagonal sections must exceed the values within

the columns and rows of that construct. When these conditions are met, the measures can be considered discriminant. Table 2 shows the difference in correlation values among the constructs, which were discovered to exceed the values of the row and column. As such, the data in this study was cleared of any problems related to discriminant validity. Figure 1 shows measurement model.

Table 1. Convergent validity

Constructs	Items	Outer Loading	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Behavioral Intention	BI_1	0.83	0.891	0.541
	BI_2	0.779		
	BI_3	0.638		
	BI_4	0.709		
	BI_5	0.648		
	BI_6	0.715		
	BI_8	0.808		
	Perceived Ease of Use	EOU_1		
EOU_4		0.803		
EOU_5		0.607		
EOU_8		0.8		
Privacy Concerns	Privacy_3	0.698	0.801	0.503
	Privacy_6	0.819		
	Privacy_7	0.641		
	Privacy_8	0.666		
Perceived Usefulness	Useful_1	0.596	0.888	0.503
	Useful_2	0.782		
	Useful_3	0.746		
	Useful_4	0.639		
	Useful_5	0.726		
	Useful_6	0.536		
	Useful_7	0.806		
	Useful_8	0.792		

** Items deleted EOU2, EOU3, EOU6, EOU7, privacy1, privacy2, privacy4, privacy5, BI1 due to lower factor loading

Table 2. Discriminant validity

Constructs	1	2	3	4
1. Behavioral Intention	0.736			
2. Perceived Ease of Use	0.656	0.719		
3. Perceived Usefulness	0.567	0.466	0.709	
4. Privacy Concerns	0.285	0.182	0.23	0.709

Figure 1. Measurement model

3.2. Structural model

In the structural model, the value of R square is 0.532 which represents how 53.2 percent of behavioural intention among the job seekers can be accounted by perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and privacy concerns. The beta coefficient in this research has indicated that there is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use ($\beta=0.489$, $std=0.054$), perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.310$, $std=0.069$) and privacy concerns ($\beta=0.124$, $std=0.047$). Additionally, the beta values revealed that only privacy concerns had a low relationship with behavioural intention (as the beta values are lower than 0.1) whereas perceived of ease and perceived usefulness were moderately correlated to behavioural intention. More analysis was conducted to investigate the significance of the relationship, examine the t-values results and perform bootstrapping procedures on 500 samples. The t-values must exceed 1.96 where significance values must be under 0.01. Table 3 shows that perceived ease of use ($t=9.111$, $p<0.01$), perceived usefulness ($t=4.484$, $p<0.01$) and privacy concerns ($t=2.625$, $p<0.01$) are statistically significant in relation to behavioural intention. In addition to that, perceived ease of use was found to be in a medium effect ($f^2=0.396$), while low effect is reflected in perceived usefulness ($f^2=0.156$), and privacy concerns (0.031), which are in alignment with the recommendations from Cohen. Thus, hypothesis 1, hypothesis 2 and hypothesis 3 were supported for this study. Figure 2 shows structural model.

Table 3. Structural validity

Relationship	Standard Beta	Standard Error	T-values	P Values	F Square	LL	UL
Perceived Ease of Use -> Behavioral Intention	0.489	0.054	9.111	$p<0.01$	0.396	0.382	0.615
Perceived Usefulness -> Behavioral Intention	0.31	0.069	4.484	$p<0.01$	0.156	0.139	0.443
Privacy Concerns -> Behavioral Intention	0.124	0.047	2.625	$p<0.01$	0.031	0.047	0.212

Figure 2. Structural model

The findings also indicate that the users consider the content, form and functionality of the websites to be convenient and easily comprehended. This is attributed to how simple the sites are to navigate and how promptly users are able to find relevant information or perform necessary tasks. Finally, the degree of control held by the users when utilizing a website or app also contributes to its usability. Comparative studies conducted highlighted that a considerable amount of existing research which adopted the TAM model discovered a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and the individual behavioural intention to utilize a system or application. This is consistent with the results discussed above.

In terms of privacy concerns, the low effect results are attributed to the possibility that employers using SNSs as a recruitment platform will be capable of accessing applicants' social media profiles in an effort to screen them or gather more information. This can happen when applications are reviewed and employers seek out the candidates' profiles. This poses a risk to employment in the case where recruiters may decide that some information they have found reveals the applicant to be an unsuitable selection. However, access to knowledge regarding the applicants' values and attachments to various social and professional groups can assist recruiters in discerning whether or not the candidate is a good match for the job position and the organization as a whole [18-25].

4. CONCLUSION

This study has expanded on existing research regarding online consumer behaviour by incorporating online recruitment tools into its scope. The study investigated the factors which impact the intention of job seekers to utilize SNSs as a platform to access work opportunities. The assessments in this study are contingent upon the TAM established by Davis in 1986. The three factors which influenced the job seekers' intention to utilize SNSs as a job seeking tool are perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and privacy concerns. Each factor has been verified as a meaningful component in job seekers' intention to utilize SNSs, and have significant relationships with job seekers' intention as validated by PLS data analysis.

In terms of the implications of this study, employers who intend to incorporate SNSs in the recruitment process must ensure that the design is convenient and any applications involved are easy to use. For example, employers should include links to job applications on SNSs which link to the organization's corporate page. This ensures that potential candidates can quickly and conveniently submit an application. The recruiters or employers can also incorporate interactive elements in SNSs so that potential candidates for the positions are able to conduct discussions or ask questions directly to representatives from the recruiting party. Finally, an organization intending to utilize SNSs in the recruitment process must establish policies which dictate the ethics and guidelines related to screening and social engagement with potential employees through the Internet. This process should begin with increasing the organization's knowledge regarding social networking. It is suggested that employees involved in recruitment be given relevant training. In this way information gathered in the recruitment process will be managed more responsibly and precisely. Organizations should also make the effort to keep the company's sites and pages up-to-date so that any information or questions from candidates can be handled quickly and efficiently.

Job seekers should take the initiative to ensure that their SNS accounts are free of information or content which they would not want a potential recruiter to see. These include personal information, photos and status updates or comments. Job seekers should also ensure that the personal information they choose to feature on SNS is accurate and updated. It is also suggested that they make connections and network with various online communities relevant to their field. Suggestions and recommendations from contacts on sites such as LinkedIn can also be a good resource for references regarding job vacancies and opportunities. The study findings indicate that the issue of privacy is concerning to many job seekers. The organization must be careful in cases where job applications are submitted online. The employees involved in recruitment must undergo the relevant training and education. This is imperative for establishing confidence and sincerity in the relationship between both parties during the recruitment process, and can result in the best possible outcomes for the hiring organization and its potential employees.

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